

Acoustic Lanes and Auditory Leads Spatio-Temporalities of Social Acoustics and Public Address Systems in Late Weimar Germany

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Abstract

Soundscape Studies are rooted in a compositional approach to space and spatio-temporal constellations (Schafer 1973). It is about notation and measurement. In this respect, doing space and sound is linked to practices, knowledge and compounds of acoustic (physical) and auditory (physiological) information. Following this perspective, noise or sound, both socially or culturally constructed, are subfunctions of what frequencies, incident energies, loudness or threshold values. Spatiality and temporality are calculable conditions. This contribution highlights another approach. It refers to two concepts, acoustic lanes (Rosenstock-Huessy 1956) and auditory leads (Anders 1992), that are derived from practical philosophy and its connections to analysis of media and interpersonal communication and to the shaping of noise and sound. Both concepts are gauging acoustic material and its information value along the lines of being 'useful' or 'applicable' or 'common' or whether it can be labelled as a 'nuisance.' Taking these designations on board, I explore the social acoustics of noise and sound in Interwar Germany when decoding public addressing systems and the evaluation of 'good' sound in urban spaces. Thereby, I challenge the polyvalent concept of acoustic branding as it has evolved since the time when instruments of signaling and alarming began competing with the polyphonies of urban streets and spaces in 1920 and 1930s Europe especially. In addition, I shed light on the modes of how the politics of acoustic management of spaces, temporal situations, moods, and masses has been conducted and professionalized. Diagnosing those relations and its contents, I do, secondly, follow the echoes that sound and noise disposed in scholarly reflections and how *émigrés* like Rosenstock-Huessy and Anders emphasized the enticing and misleading capacities of phasing audiences and publics. My notion of social acoustics is therefore shaped by the interconnectedness of behaviour, self-convergence of individuals with groups and technologies.

Introduction

Social theory deals with the presence of objects and bodies in spatial environments (Lefebvre 1967). Public spaces can be conceived of as stages for performances of any kind (Goffman 1963). The analysis of social relations is mostly bound to what one can observe (empirical data), what one wants to acknowledge and how one extracts sense from the ethnographic material that has cautiously been collected (theory). While data and agency are mostly conceptualized within the paradigm of vision, listening and hearing have been very much sidelined in social theory. This bias is also present in fields like communication and media studies and—unsurprisingly—in cultural or urban history as well. Following acoustic pathways is an occasion to shed some light on the social, cultural and economical hierarchies that frame notions of noise. Such relations establish themselves as polyvalent and polysensorial constellations (Lefebvre 1967, 30) that shape everyday social acoustics for individuals in spaces but also in terms of class. Auditory knowledge is constituted through the experience of and engagement with acoustic material. The first hypothesis of this article is that acoustic lanes and auditory leads provide directions. They mark the asymmetries that give expression to relations of power as well as to economic, political, social and cultural dominance. In this respect and as a second conjecture, I argue that noise signifies space. It imprints a signature that brands the temporal and spatial conditions of places and environments and of individual and class behaviour. Whether their texture be rural or urban, bodies and physiological receptions intertwine in constellations of sound and noise. Understanding such conditions, at least from a historian's perspective, archival materials serve as a written field recordings that refer and comprise to acoustic layers and auditory markers.

Focusing on the work of Eugen Rosenstock-Huessy (1888-1973) and Günther Stern, who later named himself Anders (1902-1992)—two scholars who fled Germany in 1933—this paper outlines their philosophical thinking concerning acoustic materialities, auditory experiences and the spatio-temporalities of noise and how this can be applied to construe social, natural or architecturally designed environments or constellations of traffic and mobility or addressing public audiences. Both authors sought to decode noise, sound, speech and music in order to understand various settings of communication but chose different approaches to do so. It is all about perception and notation. Rosenstock-Huessy, who was trained as a sociologist and lawyer, coined the term *Hörwege* (acoustic lanes) and placed the asymmetries of social relations at the center of the concept.

Anders, who became Hannah Arendt's husband in 1929, but whose plans at a career in academia were frustrated by Heidegger (Dries 2022), outlines the potential impacts of media technologies on the sensory regimes of everyday life. Coining the term *akustische Leine* (auditory lead), the philosopher considered this impact as much for the individual as with reference to class, control and consumption. Anders places men and women, in the sense of individuals, within spatial conditions of social power and hierarchies. Such positioning comes along with different modes of past and memory as well as expectations to what might occur in the present and in a contemporary environment. This perspective on spatio-temporalities leads to reckoning with the spatio-materialities of emission, exposure and nuisance.

Hörwege (Acoustic Lanes): Eugen Rosenstock-Huessy's Concept of Social Acoustics

Shortly after the First World War, Rosenstock-Huessy started working in the Department of Marketing, Advertising and Press Relations (*Literarisches Büro*) at the headquarter of the German car manufacturer Daimler in Stuttgart. He was responsible for the illustrated magazine 'Werkstatt' that addressed all members of the workforce and aimed to inform and entertain. As an editor-in-chief (Wilkins 2007), he conceptualized corporate identities and became a craftsman of corporate communication. He and his team of part-time journalists selected news and provided information for reader's eyes, ears and minds. The bi-monthly magazine nurtured discussions at shop floor level and challenged information coming from trade unions or radicalized factions on both left and right of the political spectrum. An industrial site, a company with various branches and departments was a social organisation in which opinions and ideas could propagate, along with all the positive and negative side effects this could entail. Coherence and harmony proved to be idealistic constructions that remained out of reach. At least, it was an obligation of the Press Relations Department to obtain and to successfully defend opinion leading capacities. In order to lead the discussion at shop floor level and during breaks, it became a necessary resource to persuade, to convince by modes of speech, published statements and confidence. It became key to reach diverse audiences within the workforce with various approaches. All of this was embedded in a setting of connections and relations—of hearing, speaking, listening and understanding. Starting and maintaining conversation with the workers meant negotiating different layers of access, participation and interest.

The theoretical framework of Rosenstock-Huessy's *Hörwege* is rooted in a philosophical argumentation that centers around constellations of communication, especially lanes on which words, sentences, gestures, voices and contents of speech move to the ears, eyes and minds of employees or university students. The relationship between masters and servants was no longer relevant in modern places of work and education. Instead, workers were highly specialized, and a skilled and well-trained workforce was in turn a resource for a company's success. For his employer, Rosenstock-Huessy aimed at organizing a printed, illustrated and ready-to-read format of a continuous *Betriebsversammlung*, a sort of conference that would involve the company's entire workforce, and that was elevated and transposed to a mediatized platform. As a practitioner of social communication, he hoped for making company managers and trade union functionaries meet, for presenting products as well as ordinary people which were conducting important tasks within the Daimler work environment. He outlines that all aspects of listening and all features of speaking must match and fall into another. The bonds between the different social groups of workforce and of management—and its contentions—result in calls of conformity and claims of accordance (*Übereinstimmungen*) are strong and last even a heavy dispute (*unerbittlich geführter Streit*). He idealized the identity of speech with the auditory threshold (Rosenstock-Huessy 1956, 141). In the best of cases, the messages that are disseminated by the directorate reach the recipients without any kind of distortion. Such auditory lanes combine "mouth and ear" as well as the direction of what is spoken to whom, with what intention, and how this is perceived, processed, consumed and decoded. The sociologist, remembering his own experiences with forced obedience during school lessons or while being properly drilled on a parading field during military service, as well as keeping in mind, that as a result of such harmonization, he was forced to emigrate and to leave Germany in 1933, hoping, Rosenstock-Huessy argued in favour of the civilizing capacities of the better argument and of a more convenient framing of messages, and suggested a complementary and inclusive approach to processes of communication and social relations. He labelled this field *Hörwegswissenschaft* (Ibid., 142) and conceptualized this as the territory in which the different pillars of the sciences (physiology, psychology and physics) and the humanities (sociology, history and philosophy) interact. He reflects on the way that acoustic materials are rendered present and performed (their *Vergegenwärtigungen*) and relates this to the modes, potentials and channels of auditory reception. He was searching to enable the (self-) harmonization and to nourish occasions of group belonging and are generated by abusive and manipulative leaders (Rosenstock 1925, 68). He thus applies a spatial as well as a temporal perspective to processes of speech, voices and vocal tones, hearing, listening and understanding without having an established and notorious terminology to name his approach properly. For him, sound and noise comprise an inner and an external area of social acoustics which are both linked to directions, either looking backwards to store past experiences or foreseeing future agency (Rosenstock 1924, 57).

The *Hörwege* are paved by party or trade union conventions, parish congregations, works meetings, protests in the streets and public spaces (Aulke 2015), public addresses (Szendy 2015), aggressive policing (Lindenberger 1995, 173-180) or violent routing and rioting by Freikorps or Communist militia (Stahl 2022, 301-309). In this respect, acoustic and auditory lanes are installed and adapted by force or acclamation and fixed repeatedly by consent or endorsement.

After his tenure at Daimler, Rosenstock-Huessy managed a social politics think tank and resumed a career in academia, becoming a professor of law at the University of Breslau (Wilkins 2007). As the Director of the Curriculum, he continued listening to employees, now being participants of advanced training courses at the Academy of Labour (Frankfurt/Main), or to his reading group of law students. Even if the sociologist, as a professor of law and a practitioner of jurisdiction and communication, had face-to-face social interaction in mind, he elaborated a bi-directional theoretical approach which focuses on situations and pasts. His manner of decoding the relationships of sensorial regimes can be extended to the bonds between technology and humans, as well as to the materialities of listening and hearing generated through media or in public spaces. Noise appliances, signal horns, instruments of transmission, chants, vocal offences and flout, affirmative or deviant musical repertoires (Lindenberger 1995, 334-358) and vibrating hubs of sound and urban diversities (Helms/Phelps 2016, 7-10) create materialities of social acoustics within built environments and in terms of city planning, issues of infrastructure and urban mobility.

The techno-human bonds of social acoustics (Sterne 2003, 2012) and media technologies for making sound and noise—for example a transistor or a Bluetooth box or smartphones—shape the perception of private and public space (Parzer 2008, 83-87). Even though they are supposed to be carefully designed, architecturally arranged (von Fischer 2017; Stoldt 2019) and attentively kept in order, in line and on the acoustic lane and within the auditory side rails, soundscapes are characterized by contingent, involuntary exposure to mutual-involvements (Goffman 1963, 214; Schafer 1973; Schestag 2022).

Auditory Leads:
Günther Stern's Critique of Media
Technology and Consumer Convenience Music

Günther Anders explains his concept of how individuals are tied to and enlaced by auditory leads in an anecdote (Anders 1992, 241-246). He and some friends had chartered a lodge in a natural resort where they went hiking through the forest and up the hillside. On the front side of a nearby hotel a transistor was playing music on high volume and without interruption. Every time the group caught wind of the melodies transmitted by the device the squad's mood lightened and the atmosphere tipped towards the positive. The natural sounds of their environment, however, did not have the same uplifting effect on their ears. Consuming authentic and natural acoustic information was to some extent an estranged experience that made members of the group feel unwell and insecure. When they were able to detect bits of melody, the individuals made it cohere with their common media experience and their well trained auditory expectations. They had integrated a broad variety acoustic material in their ways of perceiving the environment and used it to understand themselves as participants of world events (news), as consumers in markets of convenience and consent (advertising) and as users (disposals) who aggregate and transform what has been commercialized and monetarized beforehand. Anders detects the ties that connect people to the acoustic qualities of music, sound and noise and their capacities for (self-) bonding to its auditory values. Auditory markers create tangibilities, and thereby lead people, the common man and women in particular, and help them navigate through environments, either built, designed, imagined, contested or accelerated by technologies and devices. The terms *Hörigkeit* and *Gehorsam* describe modes of behaviour that are tethered to hierarchies of class, to modes consumption and to self-identification with the opportunities for participating in the market. These manners connect people's ears to acoustic materials and auditory markers disseminated by media technologies as well as to hearing capacities and recalls of acoustic events or the impacts of such auditory exposure.

Addressing Public Audiences: Acoustic Politics in Streets and Urban Spaces

For centuries, church bells engraved their acoustic signatures in urban spaces (Corbin 1994; Hahn 2015) and formed civic auditory memory. With the invention of sirens (Hilgers 2008; Marti 2020; Burger 2022) this primacy was contested, additionally challenged by radio devices and broadcasting consumers (Squier 2003; Birdsell 2012; Stahl 2022, 345). Since the early 1930s, public address systems (PAS) have become a game changer in terms of game of covering acoustic territories and of marking auditory sensorial regimes in urban areas (Ehlert 2005; Hauptstock/Stahl 2018, 2021). Festivities and parades serve as case studies to examine sound and noise in the public space. Celebrating the constitution of the Weimar Republic on August 11th in the late 1920s, municipal authorities reluctantly began to include free concerts, fireworks and public events in parks and marketplaces. Essen (Ruhr) was one such place that opted for such festivities. In 1927, two years after the occupation by French and Belgian troops came to an end, the mayor ordered a main event at *Saalbau*, the local concert hall, and free concerts with marching bands of the local police force, military bands and the official orchestra of city's theatre that took place in parks and places of recreation in various quarters of the city (Essen 1927, 66-70). A year later, the orchestra of the municipal police additionally performed at multiple locations across town. Representatives of the municipal and district authorities held speeches using amplifiers, microphones and loudspeakers. An acoustic lane covered the nodal points of urban space, including the public through their listening activities. Using technology to disseminate auditory experiences to female and male voters (Essen 1928, 9-11) was—at the side of consuming politics, governmental efforts and ideological advertising—a secondary way of targeting the public with information and involvement. In summer 1930, state and communal representatives in Erfurt finally decided to open up constitutional celebrations to the city's population and discussed where to position loudspeakers and to place the audience at market square when giving addresses to the public are given (Erfurt 1930, 172). In the following years, an organization of working class radio technology enthusiasts (Campbell 2019, 144; Kreis 2020, 419-423) was repeatedly asked to furnish the festivities with their self-constructed public address system (Krumm 1931; Mann 1932). Telefunken, a Siemens outlet for the emerging telecommunication and broadcasting devices market, intervened and claimed expenses and licensing fees due to copyright infringements (Gontard 1932). While the Weimar Republic was in dissolution, acoustic lanes (*Hörwege*) and auditory leads (*akustische Leinen*) were confined, delimited and exploited by economic interests. Well-established companies in the media technology sector strove to exclude other players from the profitable field of sound, audiences, acoustic material and auditory expectations and experiences (Stahl 2022, 322-325).

Long before the national socialist party seized parliamentary, administrative and governmental power in spring of 1933, the mediatization of acoustic spaces, of auditory territories and memories was already accelerating. The transition was accompanied by media technologies and the telecommunication company did endorse the NSDAP, which has been propelled from the political opposition to a place of authority, command and control. May 1st, 1933, a newly introduced Bank Holiday, was the first date for staging the capacities of the national socialist movement to harmonize and abate ongoing class conflict. In Essen, they seized the occasion to give an acoustic performance of their conception of *völkisch*—folkish and racially defined—citizenship by generating auditory tokens for applauding participants (roadside) as well as members of the Party, civil society and para-military outlets parading on the street (inside). They let the Motorcycle-Sturm-Abteilung squadron roar their engines and stood in close ranks at public places in Karnap, Steele or Altenessen to collaboratively eavesdropping broadcasts from Tempelhof field in Berlin where the NSDAP had organized an enormous congregation for the Führer (Reismann-Grone 1933). Many local dealers of radio sets supplied the Party with technological means for these public listening events and of course they claimed their expenses at the municipal authority (Radiozentrale 1933). Similar efforts took place in the city of Erfurt (Pichier 1933). Even the Head of the Catholic diocese revealed enthusiasm for what he imagined as a promising New Germany (Freusberg 1933). Loudspeakers were all over places and spaces in urban Erfurt. Acoustic material and auditory territory were marked. This technology of transmission that helped to form public audiences out of individual listeners remained a corner stone strategy for occupying and staffing communal acoustic space (Krumm 1933) throughout 1930s and 1940s Erfurt—and Essen or any other city or town in national socialist Germany. Politicians provided citizens (as consumers) with events featuring music, sound and noise (as dependents) as well as advertising ideology (as addicts) leading to acoustic branding of space and to spatial regulations of social acoustics.

Lanes Or/And Leads: Coming To Terms with Social Acoustics

When sound is read as some sort of convenient acoustic information, it reproduces fealty and allegiance among those who hear and listen. Noise nuisances, by contrast, operate differently. Even when conceived as isolated cases, they generate the desire for direct abatement, but such immediacy is rarely provided. When negotiating exposure to noxious and unsanitary conditions, the initial are regularly lost in the detail of verbose discussions. Rosenstock-Huessy and Anders, acting as seismographers of social, cultural and technological displacements, learned in what ways messages, media and biased and fabricated information relate to the sensorial preparedness of those who transfer such material into their

individual strategies for making sense of the world and their class, in the sense of socio-political environments. Married to Hannah Arendt since 1929, Anders frequently moved between different dwellings, tenancies and cities, from Potsdam to Heidelberg to Frankfurt/Main. From these locations, he sensed how the acoustic politics of public space and urban political territory shifted from conservative center-right to populist-right and *völkisch*, with strategies of racialized exclusion becoming well-established and audible in speeches and other practices for acoustically claiming the streets. He and Rosenstock-Huessy both provided accounts of what they had endured and experienced with their fellow men and women, at congregations and festivities in public and by mediated smearing campaigns or physical chivvies throughout urban spaces. Convivial gatherings and uncordial encounters, accompanied by language, tone, speech, wording, sound, gesture, acoustic threshold values and auditory material of remembrance, resulted in vocal violence and sensorial exposure long before violations of sensuous space escalated to physical assaults and bodily harm. Both authors recorded notions of everyday life, of communication and of the dispersion of acoustic materials and the apportionment of auditory contents in public space, but they leaned towards transposing those accounts into conceptual statements of how people interact with media technologies, with order and obedience. Media ecologies of branding are located in space, time and territory. As Eugen Rosenstock-Huessy and Günther Anders outlined, they are related to sensorial economies, to their space value as much as to their face value—and to a floating and mobile remembrance threshold. Public addressing systems, the temporal placement of loudspeakers in urban space, formed anthropo-technologies (Liggeri 2018, 82 and 91), containing techno-presences being double-bound to pasts and potential futures. Governing acoustic material bears opportunities to regulate range and coverage and to translate music and information into cultural matter and auditory contents. Anders and Rosenstock-Huessy can help us readers to understand that the grammar of noise and sound is spatio-temporal. It goes along lanes or leads and signifies space, participation, use, purpose, products and sensory perception of and sensuous behaviour in technologized environments.

Author Biography

Dr. Heiner Stahl is Senior Lecturer at the History Department of the University of Siegen. He published a book on popculture and media in 1960s Berlin (2010) and soundscapes, social acoustics and hearing knowledge in urban spaces in Erfurt, Birmingham and Essen from the 1880s to the 1960s (2022). He co-edited a volume on spatio-temporal relations of rhythms and timing in the processes of place/space-making (2018). In articles he has focused on noise emissions of airports (2013) and municipal hygiene and health policies in socialism (2014). He is finishing a book on media and public relations in postwar West Germany (2023) and is currently conducting a DFG-financed research project on the sensory history of ice cream, taste and table cultures in Europe from the 1770s to 1850s.

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